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ABSTRACT BOOK

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OCMB-6 DOUBLE SHELLED MOLLUSKS IN MALAYSIAN BORNEO: STATUS AND THREATS

Abdulla-Al-Asif¹, Hadi Hamli^{1*}, Abu Hena Mustafa Kamal², Mohd Hanafi Idris², Geoffery James Gerusu^{3,4}, and Johan Ismail¹

¹Department of Animal Science and Fisheries, Faculty of Agricultural Science and Forestry, Universiti Putra Malaysia, Bintulu Sarawak Campus, Jalan Nyabau 97008, Bintulu, Sarawak, Malaysia

²Faculty of Fisheries and Food Science, Universiti Malaysia Terengganu, 21030 Kuala Nerus, Terengganu, Malaysia

³Department of Forestry Science, Faculty of Agricultural Science and Forestry, Universiti Putra Malaysia, Bintulu Sarawak Campus, Jalan Nyabau 97008, Bintulu, Sarawak, Malaysia

⁴Institut Ekosains Borneo, Universiti Putra Malaysia Bintulu Sarawak Campus, Jalan Nyabau 97008 Bintulu, Sarawak, Malaysia

*Email: hadihamli@upm.edu.my

ABSTRACT

Species checklists enlist the species available within the defined geographical region and thus serve as an essential input for developing conservation and management strategies. The fields of conservation biology and ecology confront the challenge of inflated biodiversity, attributed to non-recognition of taxonomic inconsistencies. Our goals are to organize all scatter taxonomic information in one umbrella; regarding double-shelled mollusks fauna which was available in different document formats from Malaysian Borneo. An available literature survey was conducted from March 2019 to October 2020 which were published from Malaysian Borneo regions including Sarawak and Sabah states; the published taxonomic data of double-shelled mollusks species, their present conservation status, inconsistencies, habitats, research aspects, threats, conservation strategies are presented. A critical review of the checklists and distributional records of class Bivalvia from Malaysian Borneo and subsequent validation of species names with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) database revealed that the current literature with a revised checklist included 82 bivalve species from 12 order and other entities, 19 super-families and 29 families. We found 23 inconsistencies according to WoRMS and the revision of the corrected names was also presented. We found most of the enlisted double-shelled mollusks species are not evaluated by the IUCN red list authority; and found the least concern and data deficient status species in Malaysian Borneo. We evaluated, available published documents are not sufficient to decide the conservation strategies, but the paper provided some guidelines for future research, and conservation mechanisms. However, we also discussed the potential threats and their remedies for double-shelled mollusks in the enriched Malaysian Borneo ecosystem.

KEYWORDS: Bivalve, biodiversity conservation, IUCN red list, Borneo

